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Topic: Integrating SiP and long wavelength VCSEL technologies to realize a 100 Tb/s programmable link architecture for scalable and agile Metro Networks.

Abstract:

A novel Si-photonics platform for high density hybrid integration of high data rate (50 Gbps) long wavelength VCSELs and further optical and electronic components to enable cost effective and programmable DWDM links with 100 Tb/s data transmission.

As part of PASSION, a EU H2020 project, the goal is to integrate a transmitter module with 40 DWDM C-Band VCSELs together with laser driver arrays on a dense SiP chip platform, achieving a 2 Tb/s transmission capacity. Applying a modular, scalable and programmable architecture, the throughput per link can be scaled to 100 Tb/s. Advanced integration, assembly and packaging technologies will be applied to achieve a very compact and cost effective solution.



Pict 1: 8 Tb/s super module

Pict 2: Scalable link architecture

The presentation will outline and demonstrate the technological concept, focusing on the transmitter module incl. SiP technology, VCSEL components, hybrid integration techniques and scalable concept to achieve the goal of a 100 Tb/s link architecture.



Pict 1: SiP chip platform



Pict. 2: Top view SiP chip



Pict 3: Cross section SiP chip with mirror



Pict. 4+5: SC InP VCSEL 25 to 50 Gbps



SiP technologies enable a very high level of integrating several optical components, such as optical couplers, waveguides, multiplexers/demultiplexer and AWGs. Such a SOI based SiP technology has successfully been established and a new SiP chip platform (VTT, Finland) has been developed to integrate 40 DWDM VCSELs (Vertilas, Germany) and multiplex them on one fiber. Long wavelength VCSELs for C-Band and L-Band communications applications have been demonstrated for data rates of up to 50 Gbps per lane. Several modulation formats can be applied, incl. OOK, PAM4 and DMT.

Combining these two component technologies together with high performance electronics and an advanced integration solution, a power efficient 2 Tb/s transmit module in a single LGA package can be realized (in development). Furthermore, by applying wavelength tuning and a scalable concept, the individual sub-modules can be configured to realize a link with a throughput exceeding 100 Tb/s.